

THE GENESIS OF ART FRP - BASED ON THE JAPANESE TRADITIONAL SENSE OF BEAUTY-

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ABSTRACT

The history of FRP began when FRP glass fiber was used in some parts of gasoline tanks in 1942. At present, due to its high function and performance, it has a wide variety of uses, from daily necessities to aerospace products, and it has achieved remarkable developments. However, up until now, authors have only been focusing on technical advances in the quality of FRP. This study has focused on the conventionally overlooked artistic qualities of FRP. By combining superior FRP functionality, produced with advanced technology, and the unique Japanese traditional sense of beauty originating in traditional Japanese Kyo-yuzen (Kyoto-made, paste resist-dyed kimono fabric) and Ikebana (Japanese traditional flower arrangement), this study has developed these new concepts in FRP-applied products called “Art FRP”.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper would like to explain about the process and objectives behind the establishment of Art FRP and about its future development. Art FRP was born from the idea that, up until now, FRP has been researched, developed, and manufactured with a focus on functionality and practicality. Building on that, this paper focused our attention on the artistry that can be expressed, thanks to FRP’s unique qualities. More specifically, rather than simply adding on artistic elements, by combining Japan’s traditional handicrafts—for example, such craftsmanship as *Kyo-yuzen* fabric dyeing or *washi* papermaking—and applying that to FRP, authors are seeking to develop and expand FRP based on a new concept and perspective. In creating Art FRP, authors thought about what traditional crafts originated in Kyoto—a city with 1,200 years of tradition—and what artistry this study find in those crafts. This study reached the conclusion that the origin lies in Japan’s traditional tea ceremony and ikebana flower arranging.

2 WHAT IS IKENOBO?

Japan’s oldest school of ikebana, Ikenobo, began with the flowers placed on the altar of Rokkakudo, a Buddhist temple built by Prince Shotoku in 587 CE (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Rokkakudo, a Buddhist temple and Prince Shotoku.

The oldest reference to the name of Ikenobo is found in a Muromachi-era record from 1462 CE (Figure 2). That was 553 years ago. Since then, Ikenobo has adhered to the philosophy that there is splendor and radiant vitality even in withered flowers, and has created various flower arrangements in keeping with the changing times.

Figure 2: The oldest reference to the name of Ikenobo.

Figure 3 is an ikebana piece arranged in 1594 by the then headmaster Ikenobo Senko, when shogun Toyotomi Hideyoshi was visiting the feudal lord of Kaga, Maeda Toshiie. Behind the arrangement there are four hanging screens that include monkey images, and to give a sense of how large this arrangement is, the width measures 7.2 meters (nearly 24 feet). When viewed from the front, it looks like the monkeys in the scrolls to the rear are sitting on the pine boughs, and it is said to express a mountain scene. It is recorded that Hideyoshi described Senko's work as a once-in-a-lifetime achievement, or in other words, that it was a masterpiece.

Figure 3: Ikebana piece arranged in 1594 by the then headmaster Ikenobo Senko.

Now, let me introduce the three patterns that are representative of Ikenobo (Figure 4).

This is called *shoka*. The form is very simple and elegant. Ikebana arrangers present their impression of a plant's essence. There are a number of rules that must be followed.

This is called *rikka* and it has an extremely complex structure. Which style expressing the beauty of a natural landscape.

And the last of the three is *jiyuka* (Free style). This has no rules and this is the form that most faithfully reflects the aesthetic sense and philosophy of the arranger.

Figure 4: The three patterns that are representative of Ikenobo (*shoka*, *rikka* and *jiyuka*).

The concepts and expressions seen in ikebana—more specifically, the use of space, the use of asymmetry, the respect for the changing seasons, the use of simplification and exaggeration, and the incorporation of the concept of yin yang—are an aesthetic sense and value found not only in ikebana but also in all of Japan's traditional crafts and classical arts, and it is believed that these concepts and expressions are unique to Japan.

There are some examples of how these concepts and expressions are shared by the various Japanese traditional arts.

Figure 5 shows an example of the *rikka* type of ikebana at the lower left, while the image in the right is of Nijo Castle. This represents the aesthetic of asymmetry.

Figure 5: *Rikka* type of ikebana and Nijo Castle.

The respect for a sense of the seasons is also important in ikebana as well as in Japanese cuisine.

Figure 6 shows an example of *rikka* style of Ikebana at lower left. It expresses the combination of the seasonal flower material.

Figure 6: Japanese cuisine.

This is a work with a single camellia by shoka style of Ikebana, while this is one of the *Thirty-Six Views of Mt. Fuji*, a series of woodblock prints by Katsushika Hokusai (Figure 7). This represents how something can be emphasized through the deformation of that which you want to express.

Figure 7: A work with a single camellia and the *Thirty-Six Views of Mt. Fuji* by Katsushika Hokusai. The next image (Figure 8) expresses the beauty of space. The left one is rikka style of Ikebana and right one is Hasegawa Tohaku's *Pine Trees*, and it emphasizes the discovery of emotion in the blank spaces where nothing has been painted.

Figure 8: Hasegawa Tohaku's *Pine Trees*.

Ikebana consists of vases and plants, but those vases have changed over time. For example, at the far left, there is a copper vase (Figure 9). The Muromachi period was an era in which imported Chinese goods were valued, so ancient copper and imported copperware were considered to be good. Also used are naturally occurring materials such as bamboo and celadon porcelain, as well as new materials such as aluminum, glass, and acrylic.

Figure 9: Vases (Copperware, Bamboo, Celadon porcelain and Ceramics)

3 ART FRP

In this study, the conventionally overlooked artistic qualities of FRP have been focused on. By combining superior FRP functionality, produced with advanced technology, and the unique Japanese traditional sense of beauty originating in traditional Japanese *Kyo-yuzen* (Kyoto-made, paste resist-dyed kimono fabric) and *Ikebana* (Japanese traditional flower arrangement), these new concepts in FRP-applied products called “Art FRP” have been developed.

In terms of the overall harmony within *ikebana*, FRP was decided to use to manufacture the vases that play such a central role. And *Kyo-yuzen* fabric was sealed within that. In the trial manufacturing stage (Figure 10), one each of a small vase that was 20 cm in diameter and a larger one were made. In actual production, in light of FRP’s nature as being light and unbreakable, various sizes of vases were created—20 cm, 40 cm, and 60 cm, or in other words small, medium, and large.

Figure 10: The Art FRP vases.

Figure 11 shows the particular vase that has been elaborately made using the hand lay-up method [1-5] (Figure 12).

Figure 11: The particular vase in which *Kyo-yuzen* has been inserted between the FRP.

Figure 12: Hand lay up fabrication method.

Originally, glass fiber FRP has strong physical properties but looks unpleasant due to the visible glass pattern. By combining it with the Kyo-yuzen, the design takes on an appearance much like Japanese paper. This technology turns its shortcoming into its strongest advantage.

This Art FRP vase has the following four characteristics.

- 1) There were a struggle to insert the Kyo-yuzen silk cloth which, barely stretches, and make it fit neatly with the curved surface of the flower vase. However, the silk cloth carefully was inserted piece by piece, giving consideration to the characteristics of the silk fabric.
- 2) There was no use of any additives so as not to impair the transparency of the resin. However, voids and sagging of the resin are likely to occur, but various procedures and the molding technology in response to these problems have been improved.
- 3) By allowing the beautiful design of the inserted Kyo-yuzen to be seen through the FRP, Art FRP want users to enjoy the profound ancient Japanese beauty which has been unaffected by time.
- 4) In contrast to ceramics or glass vases, the light and strong characteristics of FRP enable a composition that was not possible in conventional Ikebana.

The work shown at the bottom left used 20 of the small, medium, and large FRP vases that I showed you earlier, which were connected and illuminated with LED lights. From top to bottom, the total height was 2 meters. Instead of the traditional idea of arranging flowers in the vases, FRP is enable to put the vases themselves together to construct the arrangement. This is the picture (Figure 13) of the entire arrangement. By inserting LED lighting and by spreading the arrangement out from front to back, the pattern of the *Kyo-yuzen* sandwiched inside—this violet-looking part is the pattern of the violet edge of the *Kyo-yuzen* cloth—becomes visible when the light hits it. Also the vases are divided up into upper and lower, right and left, so the vases themselves are a formation, a structure that allows this expression as if it were floating in space. This can also be considered to be a representation that relied to the maximum extent on the unique qualities of FRP—that is, it is light, sturdy, and highly transparent and permeable compared to the vases of the past made of earthenware and porcelain.

Figure 13: A work shown at the Japan Ikebana Art Exhibition in May of 2014 in Utsunomiya, Tochigi Prefecture. (Her Imperial Highness Princess Hitachi attended, acting in her position as Honorary President of the Japan Ikebana Art Association, and the Utsunomiya exhibit featured participants from 29 schools. During one week, 20,000 visitors came to the show.)

This is a work created by taking real bamboo and then making a mold from the bamboo and creating an FRP with *washi* paper from Kyoto inside (Figure 14). It is a fusion of the bamboo, which is completely natural, and a new material that was created by taking a mold of that natural element and then applying an industrial interpretation. In order to emphasize the transparent and permeable nature of FRP, LED lights were inserted inside it. By dimming the lights a bit within the exhibition hall, it brought out the extremely natural unevenness of the *washi* paper. Therefore, we had found a new expressive style according to traditional Japanese aesthetics sense.

Figure 14: A work created by taking real bamboo.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Senno Kuden, written around 1530 by Senno who was the headmaster of Ikenobo, explains, “Plants, grasses, and trees in their various forms should not be viewed solely based on their exterior aspects such as shape and color as has been done until now; they have a vitality and a radiance[6-7].” This was interpreted and conveyed as meaning, “There is splendor even in withered flowers.” These words are an affirmation of life, and indeed are an expression of a strong sense of gratitude for being alive and of wanting to use our lives to the utmost. You can sense that these words are filled with a wonderful benevolence that emerges precisely because Senno was a Buddhist. Today, people have begun to pay attention to the spirituality, thinking, and form of ikebana as a reflection of the natural environment, aesthetics, and philosophy. While ikebana is something unique to Japan, it transcends race and religion and has a profundity with which each and every one of us can empathize as human beings.

Senno taught, “Use your feet for ikebana arrangements.” By that, he meant that you should use your feet and go to the mountains and fields; see for yourself the conditions in which plants are growing and what sort of properties they have, and once you have understood the structure and personality of each individual plant, then you can arrange flowers. Ikebana means “to make flowers live.” It is not a matter of creating whatever form you happen to like. Plants already have a form and a life, so what is important is to examine them thoroughly, and with as little intervention as possible, reflect your own thoughts in the arrangement while at the same time drawing out the beauty of the plants. You have to organize your own thoughts and ideas, and think ahead of time, “What is it that I want to convey? What is the best way to convey that?” There is a saying, “The smaller the number, the more profound the emotion,” and I believe this means that when you condense your own thoughts, then you can convey your own deep thoughts by using a small number of plants in the arrangement.

It is important that traditional culture and innovational technologies support and develop each other, in turn contributing to the creation of entirely new cultures and arts. Art FRP will pursue advanced technology and artistic value, and introduce “Art FRP” to the world from the ancient Japanese capital Kyoto, where tradition and innovation coexist.

Tradition and innovation, technology and culture are not in conflict by nature; we believe that if they mutually support each other, we can progress and create a world with new thinking and values. This time Art FRP focused on vases, but in the future Art FRP plan to go beyond vases and base our work on diverse interpretations. This study will continue to carry out Art FRP’s research as a fusion of the advanced technological strength that is special to Japan and the nation’s unique aesthetic and sentiments, and Art FRP will try to convey these ideas to the world as “Cool Japan.”

The demand for FRP vases came from those in the field several years ago and they are actually being used. They are also being used in the classroom. As Japanese society is aging, there is now a very high percentage of seniors among those learning ikebana. Conventional vases are difficult to carry, though, and that had become an issue. It was asked whether there were vases that could be carried easily, that would be easy even for seniors to handle using just their own strength, and so FRP vases themselves have been used for the past few years. In this case, however, rather than just the practicality, this study focused more on the artistry, making use of the unique characteristics of FRP, and this study hope to develop it further in the future.

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